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*marina.belyh.93@mail.ru***RUSSIAN NAMING TRADITIONS**

Abstract: The article dwells on Russian naming traditions. It is shown how language and culture interact, how culture impacts naming traditions. There is given an analysis of these traditions.

Key-words: linguistic and cultural studies; Russian naming traditions; anthroponyms; personal names.

Linguistic and cultural studies (linguistic culturology, lingvoculturology – in Russia) appeared at the late of XX century as an interdisciplinary science. It currently attracts attention of many researchers. It is the most typical and popular for modern linguistics researchings.

According to Maslova [4, p. 5], this science can be determined as a science of the interaction of language and culture. The main aim of lingvoculturology is to disclose the mentality of people and its culture through language. Why is it important to explore idioms, metaphors, symbols? It's connected with the fact that they are the valuable source of information concerning culture and people mentality.

Famous Russian linguist Larin writes: «Idioms always reflect the views of people, the social system and ideology of their era indirectly. Reflect like morning light is reflected in a drop of dew». The same can be said about metaphors, symbols, etc.

One of the aspects of linguistics researching is proper names, which can be divided into such groups as toponyms, anthroponyms, homonyms, metonyms.

Anthroponyms also have several groups. Bondaletov offers four groups of proper names: personal names, surnames, nicknames, and etionyms [1, p. 86].

According to Nikonov, there can be named such groups of anthroponyms as personal names (the name given at the birth); middle names (patronymic – naming father, grandfather, etc.); surnames (generic or family name); nicknames; pseudonyms of various types, which can be both individual and group; cryptonyms

(disguised name); anthroponyms in literary works (literary anthroponymics) characters in folklore, myths and fairy tales; anthroponyms – derivatives of ethnonyms (names of nations, peoples, nations) [5, p. 58].

The author notes that among personal names there are the great number constitutes the bulk of religious names (onomastica sakra), names of apostles and evangelists: Peter, Paul, Matthew, John; angels and archangels: Seraphim, Michael, Gabriel and others; saints – generally honored (Greek, Roman, etc.): John the Baptist, Elijah the Prophet, Mary Magdalene, and Russian: Boris, Gleb, Olga, Vladimir; revered in some places – Prince Peter and Princess Fevronia in Murom.

Above all, it is necessary to define the meaning of the term «proper name».

At the Linguistic Dictionary we can find the following definition to an anthroponym, especially to a personal name: it is different from many other proper names (onima) by character customize object: each object category (people) has a name. Register names are limited. Personal names are repeated, which makes give additional naming [3, p. 42].

Ernst Pulgram in his Theory of Names attempts the ultimate precision in his definition of proper name as follows:

«A proper name is a noun used in a non-universal function, with or without recognizable current lexical value, of which the potential meaning coincides with and never exceeds its actual meaning, and which is attached as a label to one animate being or an inanimate object (or to more than one in the case of collective names) for the purpose of specific distinction from among a number of like or in some respects similar beings or objects that are either in no manner distinguished from another or, for our interest, not sufficiently distinguished» [7, p. 20].

According to the views of Superanskaya, this term refers to a word, phrase or sentence that serves to highlight the referred object from a number of similar, individualizing and identifying the object [8, p. 473].

She defines a personal name (in Old Russian as reklo, nazvische, promenovanie) as a special word for the individual and given him on an individual basis in order to be able to contact him and talk about him with others.

Zinin considers that «prior to the adoption of Christianity parents had significantly greater freedom to choose the name of the child, and the choice was characterized by external causes, sometimes random, the desire of parents to invest in the name as in the mascot, best wishes in child's future life» [10, p. 51].

Before the adoption of Christianity, Russian people took their names as «alter ego». They believed that uttering malicious behalf of someone else unkind person can lead to illness and even death called. As a consequence of this, there appeared the tradition of giving two names – real and everyday names. Real person's name was kept a secret (some of people who were close to him only knew it). Among everyday names there were names of the «fraudulent» of low-valued objects, such as a pot, a spoon. They can be divided into «protective» or «security» names which were believed to protect the child from evil forces. Sometimes parents gave so called mascots names – Virod, Drunk, Duren, Durnyaga. Among them there were a lot of words with negative prefixes not - without - Nekraso, Nekludov, Neratoff, Bezputa, Bezumny [2, p. 10].

Apart from ancient names, common Slavonic ones were used: Yaroslav, Mstislav, Vsevolod. After XIV century such names became unpopular among the princes and their approximate, and fell into disuse.

In some families in the selection of these names was also observed appellation: with the purpose to trace common components in the names of all family members.

With the adoption of Christianity, Russian met a new type of names – agionimy – names of saints.

For a long time in Russia it has been impossible to talk about any free choice of a name, since newborns were anoint according to church statutes [6, p. 142].

In addition, it is necessary to mention that the events occurred after the October Russian Revolution had influenced on the sets of names: church control (and generally any official control) over anthroponomical situation disappeared. It helped to embody full views in society on «fashionable» names.

In 1920 the name was the special pass for new people to a new life. In working communes, in the factories, it was simply impossible to give a traditional religious

name to a child, especially after separation of church and state where has been promoted atheism.

There can be noted several areas in which new names were created:

1) Revolution and the revolutionary period – Revd (revolutionary child) Revo, Hero; 2) Plans for development of the country: Ram (revolution, electrification, mechanization), Martin (in honor of the Siemens – Martin furnace); 3) Advances in science and the arts: Academe, Polygraph, Genius; 4) The names of colors and precious stones: Hydrangea, Lily, Diamond; 5) In the exercise of solidarity with the workers of foreign countries – borrowing Western names: Ernst (in honor Thalmann), Clara (after Zetkin), and Louise (in honor of Michelle).

Nowadays, the concept of name has changed again. While religion has regained the rights of citizenship, church calendars do not contribute to the identification of certain variants of names. The main one is the orthographic form of the name, and organs of civil status consider variants of the name (Natal'a and Natalia, Sof'a and Sofia) to be different names, although it is only a different pronunciation of the same name in different social groups [2, p. 12].

On the basis of works of Superanskaya, Nikonov, Suslova, we can suggest the following factors influencing the naming in Russia:

1) According to the calendar of church canonical names [8, p. 179]; 2) In honor of particularly revered saints; 3) Unmotivated hatred or love to a name [8, p. 180]; 4) Selection of the name according to the middle and last names; 5) Euphonious; 6) The effect of the ruling dynasty list of names (for example, name Catherine did not refer to be widely used at the XVIII century); 7) In honor or in memory of any person or significant event; 8) Effect of drama and literature – Assol, Aelita [9, p. 144]; 9) Increased interest in the ancient Russian history – (the use of the names of the first ancient rulers of the intelligentsia in the 20-30 years of XX century – Oleg, Igor, Vladimir, Vsevolod, Olga and others; 10) Originality – use a household name for naming – Barricade, Globe [5, p. 5 – 6]; 11) Social position - Peter, Ivan for the boyars and nobles; Petrushka, Ivashka – for the common people [1, p. 105]; Vasilisa, Thekla – for peasant women; Elizabeth, Alexandra – for noblewomen [1, p. 118].

Making a conclusion, we can say the system of the Russian naming traditions has been changing through the times. It was influenced by adoption of Christianity and Orthodox traditions of Byzantium. There are more names connected with saints, archangels, and martyrs.

Russians pay a lot of attention when choosing a name to a child. They take into account euphony and originality. More than that, there is the link with the name of a place of residence, religious affiliation, ideology. Some people give a name to their children in honour of members of the family. It is an extremely typical situation.

Some traditions have disappeared, others still exist, and new ones appear from time to time. It is important to know how cultural phenomenon influence parents' choice in a giving names to their children. It allows to follow tendencies and to try making a prediction of the future.

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